

The Members of the Sounding Board

for the FORWIT Analysis of
Austria's Higher Education System

Vienna, 3 April 2026

Dear Federal Minister Holzleitner,

At the invitation by the Austrian Council for Sciences, Technology, and Innovation, the four of us formed a “sounding board”, tasked with commenting on the council’s analysis of Austria’s higher education system. Over the past six months, we are very grateful to have had the opportunity to gain a deeper and more nuanced understanding of the state of higher education in Austria. In summary of our discussions, we would like to provide some observations that may be fruitful for your ambition to present a robust higher education strategy for 2040. We also offer a few suggestions that we believe would be useful to ensure the future sustainability of higher education in Austria, including its societal and economic effectiveness and impact.

First of all, as experts from different countries and fields, we are impressed by Austria’s continuous commitment to invest generously in higher education. Austria’s higher education system already demonstrates excellent performance in several specialist areas and possesses a broad talent base. However, societal needs are evolving, particularly in an era defined by rapid technological developments, most notably the rise of Artificial Intelligence and complex geopolitical shifts. These developments require rapid and determined action.

We believe FORWIT’s own emphasis on what Austria’s higher education system will need in 2040 is the correct one. We would like, however, to bring from our perspective the following three points to your attention and we would like to note that this letter is separate from the council’s own analysis, although it has of course been stimulated by the intense discussions held during our two day-long workshops with our FORWIT colleagues.

Our first set of remarks concern **system issues**. Austria’s differentiation of higher education institutions is a great asset. However, the institutions within its two core sectors (or tiers)—“Universitäten” and “Fachhochschulen”—would benefit from clear and aligned sector missions, which would ensure that institutions are not competing for the same space but are instead fulfilling unique societal roles (“different, but equal”). While sectors should

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be more distinguishable, you may want to improve their governance to ensure the alignment of institutional goals with national priorities. Performance agreements, when implemented properly, are a strong instrument in that regard, and also ensure differentiation within each sector. Strategically, you may want to follow other European countries in reducing the rather high number of higher education institutions overall—you may wish to consider the experiences of other countries in implementing such reforms in ways that benefit both taxpayers and the higher education system overall. As part of this ambition, we find it important to effectively prohibit the use of public funding for nominally private institutions. Furthermore, we suggest including a robust internationalization strategy, since this is essential for Austria to attract global talent and maintain scientific excellence and relevance.

The primary goal of the **educational pillar** should be ensuring that the “right students are in the right place.” To that end, we would encourage you to continue—and intensify—the ongoing process of institutional rebalancing, namely, by increasing the number of enrollment spots at “Fachhochschulen”. To support the optimization of the student journey, enhance the quality of study programs, and reduce drop-out rates, we would suggest considering the implementation of contextualized selection and admission processes for students for public universities as well. While we understand that it falls outside your direct political remit, we would like to emphasize that removal of early tracking in secondary education would allow for a more equitable and meritocratic entry into higher education. At higher education institutions, and at universities in particular, an improved staff-to-student ratios is a prerequisite for high-quality, personalized instruction. Institutional and individual incentives might help to encourage students to complete their degrees on time, while ensuring that this drive for efficiency does not compromise academic quality.

Across the globe, higher education institutions are forced to foster a more dynamic and outward-looking **research environment**. This should be addressed head-on by establishing a culture of outside-in thinking, where research agendas are informed by real-world challenges and knowledge transfer to society is treated as a core institutional priority. To do so in Austria, you may want to consider several strategic moves. Reducing block funding for research at public universities in favor of a significant increase in competitive funding pools would be a crucial step. In addition, each Higher Education Institution (HEI)

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should develop its own academic profile. This smart specialization prevents redundant research and allows institutions to become leaders in specific niches. A third aspect concerns the promotion of a diversity of career paths. In this regard, you may want to encourage creating high-status, teaching-focused tracks to complement traditional research-heavy trajectories. At the same time, we are convinced that the best and most talented scientists and scholars would benefit from introducing a Principal Investigator (PI) model, as it will empower them early in their career and increase individual accountability for project outcomes.

These are but a few observations as input for your ambition to develop a robust strategy for Austria's Higher Education System. What we have learned in the past months is highly encouraging, and yet we recognize that your task is both complex and demanding. Finally, we would like to mention that we were deeply impressed by the knowledge and expertise of FORWIT and strongly advise continued engagement with the council, including its possible involvement in the future development of the strategy document.

Sincerely,

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